

Negotiating between forest conversion, industrial tree plantations and multifunctional landscapes. Power and politics in forest transitions

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ABSTRACT

Increasing forest cover through reforestation and forest regrowth constitutes an essential contribution to mitigating the climate crisis, especially in the tropics. The Southeast Asian country of Lao PDR is on the brink of a forest transition, that is, a shift from net deforestation to net increases in forest area. This process is, however, contested and this article sheds light to power and politics in forest transitions and the implications for forests and people in Lao PDR and beyond. We develop a conceptual framework rooted in political ecology and critical state theory to identify visions and strategies by institutional actors that aim to transform the forests in particular ways, reflect on their power resources and synthesize three development projects from these strategies. We identify an antecedent dominant extractivist development project, focused on state-led timber extraction and large-scale land acquisitions. We argue that green development strategies that commodify forests through off-setting schemes, results-based payments from REDD+ and industrial tree plantations are increasingly mobilized to complement and modernize this extractivist development trajectory. Whereas these strategies align in their focus on land sparing to intensify agricultural and forest production, on the margins, we carve out an alternative livelihoods-based development project that supports extensive agroecological practices (including shifting cultivation) and integrates forests into multifunctional landscapes, re-centering local interests in reforestation approaches. The research therefore contributes to a more complex understanding of power and politics in forest transition research as well as a nuanced understanding of forest politics in political ecology.

1. Introduction

Forest transitions have been a field of intensive research in recent years, as a number of countries have transitioned from net deforestation to increases in forest area, also sparking hopes for halting or reversing global climate change (Meyfroidt and Lambin, 2011). This research has focused, for example, on transition drivers (Ashraf et al., 2017; Meyfroidt et al., 2013), enabling global policies (Lambin et al., 2014; Rudel et al., 2019) and the ecological implications of forest transitions (Alkama and Cescatti, 2016; Le Noë et al., 2020; Magerl et al., 2019). Especially in the tropics, reforestation and forest restoration are seen as an important contribution to climate change mitigation (Meyfroidt and Lambin, 2011), resulting in global initiatives such as REDD+ and the increasing promotion of industrial tree plantations that often compete with agrarian and

industrial land use change (Butler et al., 2009; Fox et al., 2014; Ingalls and Dwyer, 2016). The potential contribution of forest carbon sequestration looms large in Asia Pacific, where REDD+ investments are estimated to contribute up to 40% of global sequestration (FAO, 2010).

Whereas research has highlighted state interventions as drivers of forest transitions (Lambin and Meyfroidt, 2010; Rudel et al., 2019), less attention has been paid to the messy, power-laden pathways through which these transitions occur (Riggs et al., 2018). This article unravels the ongoing forest transition in Lao PDR (Laos) and analyzes the politics of increasing forest cover. The land-locked and mountainous Southeast Asian country is on the brink of a forest transition (Gingrich et al., 2019; Köhl et al., 2015).¹ The Government of Lao PDR (GoL) has committed to forest expansion since the 1990s, aiming at 70% forest cover by 2020 (MAF, 2005). Despite high-level political consensus on forest expansion,

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¹ International FAO data has documented net increases in forest cover since 2000 (Köhl et al., 2015), whereas national inventories still see slight decreases in forest land. The different assessments result from differing definitions of forests. FAO data defines forests as land area with a tree canopy cover of more than 10% as opposed to 20% in national statistics in Laos (Ingalls et al., 2018, p. 97).

actual reforestation and forest policies are contested while gains in forest area remain fragmented.

We refer to the heuristics of “political forests” to understand how forests are produced as “dynamic spaces and political ecologies” (Peluso and Vandergeest, 2020, p. 1083). We develop a conceptual framework rooted in critical state theory to identify some of the “political forest-making processes” through analyzing the competing interests, strategies, visions and power relations that shape forest transitions in Laos. To analyze these strategies, we draw on critical policy analysis (Brand, 2013; Buckel et al., 2014) to carve out strategies on how social forces (e.g., state institutions, NGOs, donors, companies) try to influence forest politics, that is, how they aim to transform the Laotian forests and people’s interactions with these forests, reflect on their power resources and synthesize three development projects from these strategies. We develop a power-laden trajectory of how reforestation and forest conservation have entered forest politics in Laos and have shaped the ongoing forest transition. We argue that a dominant extractivist development project (Brand and Dietz, 2014; Pichler, 2014) is increasingly complemented and modernized through the emergence of green development strategies that aim to gain power through commodifying forests for a more efficient and long-term accumulation in the course of carbon sequestration. As we show, the extractivist and the green development project complement each other as they are based on the separation of agricultural and forest lands – consistent with the paradigm of “land sparing” – that effectively marginalizes those use(r)s relying on multifunctional landscapes (Castella et al., 2013; Ingalls and Dwyer, 2016; Pichler et al., 2021a). We therefore sketch the contours of a livelihoods-based development project that seeks to challenge this separation by integrating across the farm-forest continuum to create space – both in policy and on the land itself – for alternative modes of development and forest conservation rooted in multifunctional landscapes (Dressler et al., 2016).

The article proceeds as follows: The next section introduces a conceptual framework and methodology for analyzing politics and power in forest transitions from a political ecology and critical state theory perspective. In Section 3, we apply this framework to analyze strategies and their power resources to transform the Laotian forests and synthesize three development projects from these strategies. Section 4 then discusses the implications of this analysis for forests and people as well as for the role of power and politics in forest transition research in Lao PDR and beyond. The article therefore aims to better understand forest transitions as power-laden processes and critically scrutinize forest-related programs and policies with regard to their powerful yet unequal implications for different people and territories. In particular, it allows us to reconceptualize the divergent, overlapping and contested nature of various reforestation strategies – their origins, intents, and outcomes – and analyze the points along which they both converge and diverge, and to what effect. In doing so, we contribute to the interdisciplinary advancement of forest transition research (Kull, 2017; Kull et al., 2007; Lestrelin et al., 2014; Riggs et al., 2018; Turner and Robbins, 2008) as well as to political ecology research on forests in analyzing how politics play out in current strategies to mobilize and transform forests in particular ways (Creak and Barney, 2018, pp. 704–705; Peluso and Vandergeest, 2020, pp. 1089–1092).

2. Analyzing forest transitions from political ecology and critical state theory

In the last decade, political ecology research on Southeast Asia – as elsewhere – has paid particular attention to accelerated processes of land grabbing (Dwyer and Vongvisouk, 2019; Fox and Castella, 2013; Keene et al., 2015; Schoenberger et al., 2017; Zoomers, 2010). Scholars have associated large-scale land acquisitions with the concurrent consolidation of (authoritarian) neoliberalism and resource-led development strategies that favor the dispossession and exclusion of local people from their territories (Einzenberger and Schaffar, 2018; Hall et al., 2011; Kenney-Lazar, 2019). These developments have often accelerated the

continuous decline of forests since the beginning of the 20th century (Davis et al., 2015; Ingalls et al., 2018). At the same time, international climate governance increasingly aligns reforestation with more traditional development aspirations in the course of green growth and the green economy (Barney, 2012; Corbera et al., 2017; Kenney-Lazar et al., 2018b; Scheidel and Work, 2018). These processes imply constant changes in how states and politics mobilize and transform forests.

In Laos, politics are often treated as synonymous with the forms and functions of the Lao People’s Revolutionary Party (LPRP), thereby reproducing the narrative of a monolithic and unified actor. Political ecology and ethnographic research, however, have contributed to a more complex understanding of the Lao state in focusing, for example, on the local perception, manifestation and reproduction of the state (High, 2014; Singh, 2012) or the strong divide between state policy and practice (Fujita and Phengsopha, 2008; Smits and Bush, 2010). There is less research, however, that analyzes the contested nature of national political strategies and development projects itself and grounds these in broader political economy explanations (for exceptions, see, e.g., Dwyer et al., 2016; Suhardiman et al., 2019). To analyze the contested nature and power relations that drive the control of natural resources, and forests in particular, we draw on critical state theory.

According to critical state theory, the state serves essential conditions for organizing capitalist relations (Görg and Brand, 2006; Jessop, 1990; Poulantzas, 1978). In Laos, political scientists refer to this seemingly paradox of authoritarian one-party rule and the expansion of market forces as “market Leninism” or the “Leninist road to capitalism” (Creak and Barney, 2018, p. 708). Even in the most authoritarian political settings, however, the state and its associated institutions are a terrain across which social actors struggle to gain influence and legitimacy by pursuing political strategies that serve their interests and agenda. In this context, *state projects* describe relatively coherent bundles of strategies, actions and discourses that pursue similar interests in a given field of politics (Buckel et al., 2014, p. 46; Jessop, 1990, p. 268). With regard to natural resource politics, we refer to such state projects as *development projects* (Andreucci, 2017; Pichler, 2014).

To analyze such development projects, Jessop et al. (1988, pp. 158–161) differentiate between accumulation strategies and state strategies. An *accumulation strategy* describes a specific strategy of economic growth – or the economic foundation of a development project – and the respective prioritization of economic sectors and interests. *State strategies* constitute the policies, regulations and institutions conducive to the stable reproduction of this economic development model (Pichler, 2015, p. 513). These also comprise legitimizing discourses and actual material arrangements that regulate how specific societal groups benefit from the course of development. In the absence of procedural legitimacy through democratic elections, one-party regimes “seek to generate legitimacy by mobilizing popular consent” (Creak and Barney, 2018, p. 702), for example, through revenues and infrastructural development from mining or hydropower or through integration into patronage-based rent seeking systems. Without ‘input legitimacy’ through elections, the state has to provide ‘output legitimacy’ by guaranteeing personal (material) benefits (Singh, 2012, p. 158) or the achievement of public goals that demonstrate the effectiveness of the administration.

Grounded in critical state theory, we develop a conceptual framework for analyzing forest politics (Fig. 1). We adopt the term *accumulation strategy* to analyze political-economic drivers (e.g., financial gains for carbon sequestration) whereas we refer to *political-spatial strategies* when describing strategies and policies that aim to mobilize and transform the forests in specific ways. Beyond narrow state representatives, analyzing state strategies as *political-spatial strategies* acknowledges the diverse institutional actors that influence and co-constitute the course of development and indeed the state itself (Creak and Barney, 2018, pp. 707–708), including private companies, international (donor) organizations or development cooperation. At the same time, analyzing strategies as *political-spatial strategies* accounts for the territorial and material dimension of these strategies. Hence, these strategies transform

Fig. 1. Conceptual framework for analyzing institutional actors' strategies and power resources to influence state policies (own illustration).

forest landscapes in particular ways (e.g., through tree plantations or agroforestry), characterizing the state as an “environment-making state” (Creak and Barney, 2018, p. 706). From these strategies that different institutional actors mobilize, we abstract development projects as relatively coherent bundles of strategies and visions.

In influencing state politics, that is, in inscribing strategies and visions in policies and (state) institutions, actors are equipped with unequal power resources. Adapted from Buckel et al. (2014, pp. 49–51), we differentiate between institutional, systemic and discursive resources. *Institutional resources* comprise the technical, administrative and financial capacities of (state) institutions as well as military or other authoritative or bureaucratic means (see also, Creak and Barney, 2018, p. 700; Hlaing, 2006). With more explicit regard to accumulation strategies, *systemic resources* refer to the capability of actors to provide or remove capital, finance or labor. Systemic resources also comprise “infrastructural resources” that Creak and Barney (2018) define as the (perceived) “capacity to develop” (p. 703) and include material benefits that – if not actually achieved – seem at least achievable (see also, Singh, 2012, pp. 155–160). *Discursive resources* are mobilized when actors integrate their interests and strategies with dominant and broadly accepted discourses of prosperity and progress that legitimize, for example, the marginalization of shifting cultivation (Singh, 2012).

Since the establishment of the Lao PDR in 1975, the LPRP has been the dominant policy organ of the state, subordinating and relegating the government and its respective bureaucracy to the execution of Party directives (Stuart-Fox, 2006, pp. 64–65). Observers of Laos' political system have accordingly characterized the prevailing legal framework as largely one of rule-by-decree rather than rule of law (Dwyer et al., 2016). At the same time, the paradox of authoritarian rule and weak institutional capacity “demonstrate that the Laotian state is not static” (Hlaing, 2006, p. 129). Rather, it is a more shifting, negotiated landscape of both convergent and divergent interests that nevertheless coalesce and are expressed through the political directives of the Party.

Taking the mobilization of forests as an empirical case, the conceptual framework allows to identify different – yet often aligning – accumulation strategies and corresponding political-spatial strategies and how these mobilize forests with different power resources and therefore shape the outcome of forest transitions in specific ways. The analysis follows a qualitative research design that is based on 22 interviews conducted during two research stays in November 2019 and in February and March 2020 with representatives of state institutions (12 interviews), international (donor) organizations (4), companies (4), and NGOs (2) in Laos. In the interviews, we asked these representatives about the general context of reforestation and forest regrowth in Laos, the respective policies and strategies as well as conflicts and alliances. Depending on the interview partners and in the course of the interviews,

we specified the interview guideline to better understand specific strategies and policies and their implications (e.g., tree plantations, REDD+, land use planning). We conducted most of the interviews in English but had collaboration partners and research assistants that helped with interview appointments, institutional contexts and translation. To keep anonymity, we numbered the interviews but provided institutions and functions where necessary. Participant observation from two stakeholder workshops on land tenure and the UNFCCC implementation as well as informal conversations further informed the analysis.

The interviews were transcribed and analyzed via atlas.ti. We coded emergent themes along both emic (those deriving from the interviewees themselves) and etic (those we developed through careful scrutiny of participant meanings) categories to synthesize divergent, overlapping and contested strategies and visions to transform the forests. In the course of the analysis, we abstracted the three development projects and their manifestation in policies, regulations and institutional structures and processes and aligned the most important actors to these projects. Hence, the ex-post assigned development projects are analytical abstractions rather than clear-cut empirical phenomena. They may comprise actors and strategies that explicitly refer to one another but also some that do not see themselves explicitly aligned (Buckel et al., 2014, p. 46). The most important – interpretative – criteria for assigning strategies, policies and institutions to a certain development project is whether they share a common development direction on how to mobilize and transform the forests. The description and analysis of the power-laden dynamics of forest transitions in Laos were enriched with data from political programs, documents and policies as well as peer-reviewed literature. While the methodology is suitable for understanding power and politics on a more strategic state and policy level, we are not able to grasp the actual implementation and manifestation of these politics on the ground and in specific local circumstances as these themselves rely on the outcome of fine-grained power politics and conflicts.

3. A power-laden forest transition trajectory: development projects, strategies and power resources to transform the forests

In the following section, we apply this conceptual framework to forest politics in Laos and carve out the power-laden trajectory of the ongoing forest transition in analytically abstracting three different development projects. We discuss the ways in which these development projects intersect with one another, sometimes diverging, sometimes converging, and identify dominant actors and power resources within larger structural dynamics of change along the forest transition.

3.1. From timber revenues to large-scale land concessions: features of the dominant extractivist development project

We first describe what we call an extractivist development project that has emerged as the dominant form of controlling and transforming forests through timber extraction and large-scale land concessions since the mid-1970s. After years of armed conflict leading up to 1975, the new government sought to establish central territorial control over the vast forests and commodify them for urgently needed state revenues (Kenney-Lazar, 2019; Stuart-Fox, 2006). Logging and security concerns, especially in the borderlands, have thus driven state control over the forests in these early years, especially through declaring and zoning forests as state land. Three umbrella military-controlled state enterprises in the north, center and south of the country tightly controlled logging as well as (un)documented timber export (Stuart-Fox, 2006, p. 61). Beginning in the 1990s, the government started a comprehensive zoning process to categorize state forest lands into production, protection and conservation forests, together ultimately comprising 12.5 million ha of land or more than 50% of the national territory (Lestrelin et al., 2013, p. 24). Not all of these state forest lands are forested, and many of these areas comprise villages with paddy fields and other agricultural or extractive land uses. At the same time, more than 3 million ha of forests

are located outside of these state forest lands, comprising, for example, industrial tree plantations on areas designated as agricultural land (Lestrelin et al., 2013, p. 5; MAF, 2005, pp. 4–12). Consistent with global forest conservation initiatives emergent from the 1985 Tropical Forest Action, conservation goals in Laos continued to take shape through an increasingly professionalized state forest service throughout the 1990s and 2000s, wherein state control over forest areas remained the core concern (Ingalls, 2017; Salter and Phanthavong, 1989).

Throughout this period, the government framed shifting cultivation as a key obstacle to modern statehood, timber extraction and conservation goals. Since 1989, the Shifting Cultivation Stabilization and Permanent Occupation Program initiated diverse policies and activities to eradicate shifting cultivation (MAF, 2005, p. 39). The 2007 revision of the Forestry Law further targeted shifting cultivation in introducing additional forest categories to designate these areas for natural regrowth (regeneration forests) or active tree planting (degraded forests) (MAF, 2005, p. 11; National Assembly, 2007, p. Art. 33). Furthermore, in the mid-1990s two regulations officially started a comprehensive land and forest allocation (LFA) program. PM Decree No. 186 and MAF Instruction No. 822 aimed at replacing shifting cultivation with permanent agriculture through agricultural land allocation and titling, and to sustainably use forests through concrete local forest zoning (e.g., through the allocation of village forests). Until the early 2000s, more than 9 million ha of land were allocated with three-year temporary land use certificates to 6830 villages, representing more than half of all villages in the country (MAF, 2005, pp. 5–6). The LFA program, while conferring a degree of formalization to local land and forest claims, also functioned to circumscribe these claims, effectively demarcating and limiting local land use to pave the way for direct state administration of ‘non-village’ territory (Barney, 2009; Vandergeest, 2003).

State territorialization and the LFA program sought to transform multifunctional landscapes into separate agricultural and forest lands, creating the prerequisite for the expansion of commercial agriculture and other extractivist activities (Pichler et al., 2021a). Since the end of the 1990s, state-controlled forestry and conservation has, therefore, co-evolved with an unprecedented expansion of large-scale private land concessions. Both rely on the commodification of forests (for timber, mining, hydropower, cash crops) to raise state revenues for infrastructure and services provision (Ingalls et al., 2018, p. 104). Similar to timber trading routes, the neighboring countries of China, Vietnam and Thailand stimulate the accumulation strategy as they drive investments through FDI and absorb commodity exports (Ingalls et al., 2018, p. 104). Since the mid-2000s, this accumulation strategy has been linked to the so-called Turning Land Into Capital (TLIC) policy (Kenney-Lazar et al., 2018a). The TLIC policy has pushed private land concessions and leases as the most important political-spatial strategy to accelerate the extractivist development project, spanning more than one million ha of land. Almost half of these concessions, 593,357 ha, are contracted for agricultural and tree plantations, followed by more than 40% or 415,527 ha of land for mining concessions (Hett et al., 2020). At the same time, recent years have seen a massive increase in contract farming that increasingly complements large-scale land acquisitions for cash crops and tree plantations,² especially in the northern provinces (Friis et al., 2016; Ingalls et al., 2018, p. 92; Kallio et al., 2019; Kenney-Lazar et al., 2018b).

The extractivist development project has emerged as the dominant policy direction since the 1990s. This dominance is reflected in Party documents and the Prime Minister’s decrees as well as in directions and documents by leading ministries such as the Ministry of Energy and Mines (MEM), the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry (MAF) or the Ministry of Planning and Investment (MPI) (interview 2, 4, 7, 8, 20). The extractivist development project has built its dominance on its systemic

resources of Turning Land into Capital, that is, FDI from booming neighboring economies have driven private large-scale land acquisitions and bestowed high economic growth rates (Hett et al., 2020, p. 28). The respective separation of people from forests through state territorialization has furthermore drawn on discursive resources on the supremacy of sedentary agriculture and industrial forestry over shifting cultivation and other extensive land-use practices. Nevertheless, conflicts and political interventions as well as decreasing return on investments in the last decade indicate that the expansion of large-scale land concessions also shows cracks. Mounting evidence on increasing land conflicts led the government to announce several concession moratoria between 2007 and 2012. The latest and most targeted, PM Decree No. 13/2012, prohibited new concessions for rubber, eucalyptus and mining exploration until the end of 2015 (interview 1, 9, 19). At the same time, the amended Land Law of 2019 limits concession length (50 years) and extent to account for these problems (National Assembly, 2019, p. Art. 29, 120). Furthermore, companies are required to survey and map out the actual land area *before*, rather than after the concession is approved (Kenney-Lazar et al., 2018a, pp. 20–24). These interventions – together with the low return on concession investments due to corruption, poor management or oversupply (especially in hydropower electricity production) (interview 2, 19, 20, 21) – have indeed slowed down concession expansion, leading a representative from an international donor organization to conclude that “the concession machine is broken” (interview 16). Whereas extractivist concessions still expand into the forests, green development strategies are increasingly mobilized to complement and modernize the extractivist development trajectory.

3.2. Modernizing the extractivist trajectory: offsetting, REDD+ and industrial tree plantations

Drawing on Peluso and Vandergeest (2020), we frame the emerging green development project as corresponding to “the growing importance and attention to organized forest conservation and tree crop plantations, contrasting with the more hegemonic forms of extraction and production forestry” (p. 1089). In doing so, its proponents aim to avoid the further degradation of forest resources but still boost economic growth and attract FDI and international funding for modernizing the extractivist trajectory. According to government representatives, “in the green growth strategy, the land could be a capital as well ... but please use it more efficiently. These [TLIC and green growth] ... complement one another, not constrain but complement one another” (interview 21). Revenues from ‘quality investments’ remain important, whereas offsetting for more traditional extractivist activities and results-based payments from REDD+ represent additional strategies to compensate for highly destructive extractivist activities.

While both the extractivist and the green development project tend towards centralized state control over forests, international programs and donor agencies shape the commodification of forests for carbon sequestration. The UNFCCC and related programs (e.g., REDD+) and financial mechanisms (e.g., the Green Climate Fund) account for important drivers of green development strategies. As a representative of an international organization in Vientiane confirms:

I think a lot has to do with people like us, international partners. ... An international process like the UNFCCC coming along and saying the country should have an NDC [Nationally Determined Contributions], or UNFCCC coming along and saying you should work on REDD+, so they work on it. ... So probably these documents make a lot of sense to us, but what does it mean to the government? Probably very little. (interview 9)

At the same time, the notion of Laos’ green development project as an opportunistic grab for donor funding misses the point. Mentioned earlier, Laos’ tendency to front-end its unified image is belied by a high degree of internally divergent voices and agendas. The GoL seeks both to

² In the so-called 3+2 model, the investor provides capital/inputs, technology and an (export) market, whereas the farmer provides land and labor (interview 8).

respond to international climate governance – bolstering its credentials as a global player, a message that rings loudly back into the domestic space – and at the same time derive alternative financial resources to support its development agenda. Furthermore, Laos' commitment to the 70% forest cover goal, for example, is rather antecedent to the emergence of the global green agenda. In an important sense, this goal is held as a litmus test for the effectiveness of the Party's administration in Laos, enshrined not only in specific outward-looking political commitments, but also often-reiterated internal directives.

Offsetting schemes for extractivist activities as well as results-based payments from REDD+ comprise important political-spatial strategies of the green development project. Offsetting schemes, such as for hydropower, are well-aligned with the dominant development trajectory as they rely on payments from extractivist activities to fund reforestation and conservation programs (interview 11). According to government representatives from different ministries, for every hectare of forest destroyed, companies are meant to pay USD 800 dollars in order to replant trees or monitor natural regeneration elsewhere. Additional long-term payments of 1% of revenues to the Environmental Protection Fund (EPF) should furthermore enable the management of these reforested areas as well as forest protection, conservation and rehabilitation (interview 2, 4, 11, 16, 18, 22). There is, however, doubt surrounding the effectiveness of offsetting schemes in practice. Sometimes, project developers finance forest restoration by direct payments to local communities to incentivize them to abandon shifting cultivation in restoration areas.³ In other cases, developers and government agencies jointly finance protected area management.⁴ While proponents cite these activities to demonstrate improved practice, there are few confirmed examples. The notoriously intransparent EPF remains largely financed – at around 95% – by the World Bank (interview 9, 16).

In addition to these offsetting schemes, results-based payments from REDD+ have established as an important political-spatial strategy to push for the green development project. Unlike offsetting schemes that are mostly individual and place-specific projects, REDD+ aims to implement comprehensive, long-term and nation-wide mechanisms to prevent emissions from deforestation and forest degradation. To support its target of 70% forest cover, the GoL has used the international financial, institutional and technical resources from REDD+ to establish a bureaucratic apparatus that links the international program with national priorities and prepare for results-based payments. In 2020, the Green Climate Fund approved to pilot such payments for over 8.4 million tons of emission reductions per year (USD 5/ton) for six upland provinces in the north of Laos (interview 16). For the period of 2020–2025, this would equal USD 42 million. While this appears to represent a significant volume of funds for REDD+ activities, USD 42 million for two million people in the six northern provinces amounts to only USD 21 dollar per person for five years (interview 16).⁵ The final contract volume was considerably less, though further financing is under discussion.

Hence, systemic resources – but also personal resources of key government institutions – still largely align with the extraction of natural resources (Vongvisouk et al., 2016) as private investments in extractive industries far outweigh results-based payments and offsetting for reforestation and forest conservation. As a company representative confirms:

All of that stuff [carbon credits and the like], you can't build a business on that when your regulatory environment is that loose. You have to build a core business that stands by itself. (interview 15)

Furthermore, offsetting schemes somewhat depend on extractivist industries to channel financial resources for protected areas and reforestation. As a conservation officer in DOF confirms:

We benefit from development, I mean somewhere money has to come from to manage the protected areas, so actually these [extractivist] investments also bring some opportunities. ... Otherwise it's difficult to finance protected areas. (interview 11)

In this power configuration, the promotion of industrial tree plantations can be seen as a green development strategy to capitalize on these systemic resources and combine environmental and economic concerns. PM Order 9 in 2018 and MAF Ministerial Instruction 1758 in 2019 opened 600,000 ha of degraded state forest land (within the National Production Forest Areas) for private tree plantations to establish a domestic tree plantation industry and increase forest cover at the same time (World Bank, 2019, p. xi). Eucalyptus and acacia account for the most important fast-growing trees that are planted in a 7-year cycle. Currently, four key companies (Scandinavian Stora Enso and Burapha, Australian Mekong Timber Plantations⁶ and Chinese Sun Paper) actively develop tree plantations and wood-processing facilities, with many more companies expected to take advantage of the new possibility (interview 7, 13, 20). Hence, when results-based payments for carbon sequestration remain low, the forest transition rather materializes from increased tree plantations (that provide economic benefit) than from naturally regenerated forests (that are encouraged through REDD+). Increasing international reforestation efforts in the course of climate change mitigation strategies seem to give private tree plantations a further boost, as a conservation officer in DOF describes: “[Plantation forestry] was always there on paper, but it's more prominent that the government now tries to take action and ... promote it more actively. So, I think there is a big movement in this” (interview 11). A representative of an international organization confirms the importance, pointing to the high-level domestic policy initiative rather than sole international pressure: “The prime minister has opened up concessions to private companies in production forest areas and this seems to be a very key kind of direction in forestry” (interview 9). Likewise, a private tree plantation company frames the decision as a cornerstone for its lobbying efforts:

This organization has been lobbying the government for a long time. And now, now it starts seeing the fruits of that. ... I think we're making good progress. We were planting 1000 ha this year ... so, [only] 4000 ha in nine years, and then 1000 ha in [just] one. It's really going up now. (interview 15)

Yet, the cautious power gains of the green development project lie not only in its strategic alignment with extractivist financial flows through offsetting and industrial tree plantations but also in its alliance with discursive power resources of turning ‘degraded’ shifting cultivation landscapes into more productive use, either for payments from REDD+ or industrial tree plantations. As we have shown above, these discourses have shaped forest and natural resource politics for decades, framing shifting cultivation as a “desperate agricultural practice” and a “low-margin activity” that “doesn't have a lot of future” (interview 16). For REDD+, the selection of six northern provinces, where shifting cultivation plays a major role, emphasizes the government's aim to merge conservation efforts with the expansion of sedentary agriculture in the course of eradicating shifting cultivation (interview 3). For industrial tree plantations, the 600,000 ha of degraded state forest lands

³ Such as the Theun-Hinboun Hydropower Project in central Laos, where villagers were paid USD 15/ha in compensation (interview 14).

⁴ Such as the World Bank-financed Nam Theun 2 power plant that enabled the establishment of Nakai-Nam Theun Park, the first national park in Laos (interview 18).

⁵ According to the benefit sharing agreement, 50% should go to the village fund, 20% to the District Agriculture and Forestry Offices (DAFO) to finance extension work and the rest to the government budget (interview 16).

⁶ Mekong Timber Plantations changed name and owner only recently. In 2017, it took over the plantation concessions from Japanese Oji that established most of its plantations between 2005 and 2010.

mainly comprise multifunctional landscapes that are neither clearly agricultural nor forest lands but change their function according to rotations. A large proportion of these lands are located in state forest land and the national maps just ‘write out’ their local use. As an international consultant explains:

If you look at a map of the land of the Department of Forestry, between 30 and 40% of the country is potential forest, that’s what’s mapped out but that’s not land cover, that’s the hope [...] But it’s not degraded, it’s used for agriculture. [...] So, in some cases it’s degraded and abandoned⁷ but in some cases, ... it’s used. It’s hard to say how much percentage is which, but I would say probably in the order of 25% is actually degraded and abandoned and about 75% is part of the rotational upland cultivation. (interview 17)

Hence, the green development project follows a land sparing paradigm that is likely to further exclude local land users from multifunctional landscapes in favor of state-controlled conservation schemes and private industrial tree plantations. This is because villagers in state forest land still lack recognition of their land use practices, giving state institutions at different scale the power to write out their existence and separate them from the forests.

3.3. A livelihoods-based development project at the margins: participatory land-use planning in multifunctional landscapes

The following section discusses the contours of an alternative development project that aims to integrate the multifunctional landscapes and their users into a vision of livelihoods-based forests, ranging from shifting cultivation to the subsistence and commercial use of agrobiodiverse species, including Non-Timber Forest Products (NTFP) (interview 10, 12, 19). Rather than separating people from forests and therefore marginalizing the local livelihood practices of Lao upland people, proponents stress the multifunctionality of landscapes that provide for livelihoods alongside ecosystem services. As “the Lao are still farmers” (interview 19), that is, as much as 80% of the workforce is engaged in agriculture (Ingalls et al., 2018, p. 80), the accumulation strategy puts food security – through both lowland paddy rice and upland shifting cultivation – center-stage and aims to lessen the dependence on external markets and foreign investments (interview 10, 19).

Due to the importance of multifunctional landscapes for local livelihoods, the key political-spatial strategy rests upon participatory land use planning that is able to integrate the multi-purpose uses and complex land tenure arrangements on the ground. Since 2011, The Agro-Biodiversity Initiative (TABI) has developed a Participatory Forest and Agriculture Land Use Planning, Allocation and Management tool (pFALUPAM) that aims to integrate these multifunctional landscapes to carve out space for these both on the landscape and within national policy (Dwyer and Dejongsa, 2017). At the moment, it is mainly NGOs and selected researchers and development assistance that support land sharing and multifunctional landscapes as viable livelihood strategies (Vongkhamho et al., 2019). While institutional, systemic and discursive power resources of the GoL and the Party strongly rest upon centralized control over forests and land sparing strategies, district and village authorities as well as parts of MAF and the National Assembly, however, cautiously recognize the legitimacy of livelihoods-based strategies (interview 10, interview 17) as the institutional and spatial integration of multifunctional landscapes meets practical concerns of local authorities and upland farmers:

When you work at the local level, everybody knows the reality, ... they will not say, you have to stop [shifting cultivation] because they

know they have to ensure food security, and they know that it’s the only solution. (interview 12)

The partial recognition of local land use maps – and the acknowledgement of shifting cultivation practices in these maps – therefore show tentative institutional and discursive power gains.

Whereas the local grounding is indeed a major resource for the livelihoods-based development project, it is thus far also a serious limitation as the strategic interventions fail to scale up in dominant provincial or national maps. For example, the recently agreed National Master Plan on Land Allocation that, for the first time, presents a central map that assigns all land to a specific purpose (Suhardiman et al., 2019) does not contain any reference to multifunctional landscapes. However, upscaling – that is, integrating these land use plans into national maps and strategies – is highly important as conflicting interests often come from central level investment decisions that do not communicate with the district level (roundtable meeting, February 2020). This is exemplified through conflicts over the recognition of villages and their diverse livelihood practices in state forest land. In 2014, local land use planning efforts proved successful when the National Assembly asked the GoL in a Notice (NA Notice No 273/2014) to review the three forest categories and exclude villages as well as their agricultural and communal forest lands from state forest land. Following TABI’s piloting of such re-delineation in one province, the World Bank approved to support the effort and the Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment (MONRE) agreed to implement the effort on the ground. When the project proposal was translated from English into Lao, however, the GoL omitted the part on the re-delineation of state forest land. After some months, the World Bank stopped the project when it became clear that the GoL would not recognize the livelihood practices of these villages. At the same time, the controversial negotiations on the new Land Law circled around the same issue. Following failed attempts to craft a revised Land Law through a multi-stakeholder process, the Party released a revised Land Policy that, while confirming existing commitments to the recognition of customary tenure in general terms, did not go so far as to clarify what this would mean, particularly as also reasserted state privilege over state forest areas which, the policy reaffirmed, would cover 70% of the country (interview 17).

Although participatory land use planning provides an important political-spatial strategy, it is not enough to support an alternative development pathway, especially due to strong pressure for land commodification from booming neighboring economies. As a representative from the Department of Agricultural Land Management of the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry (DALAM/MAF) states: “It’s nice to do the zoning but you need to think further about investments. ... Not just doing the plan and then go to the next place” (interview 19). Hence, to increase systemic resources – and indeed compete with the commercial pressure from extractivist industries – the commodification of NTFP and other local species and cultivars can be seen as a strategy to upscale multifunctional land-use practices. Typical NTFP include cardamom, bamboo, different kinds of mushrooms, berries or teas. While the term implies that these species are explicitly linked to forests, they derive from a much broader set of land uses including agricultural fields, fallows and forests of various successional stages. Paradoxically, in the Lao context at least, forests do not appear to be the primary sources of these. Rather, mosaic landscapes of shifting cultivation fields and fallows provide more NTFP than old-growth forests. Preliminary analysis from TABI’s survey of more than 3000 households in northern Laos indicates that fully 48% of income generated from the sale of NTFP derive from rotational cultivation systems (including fallows and secondary vegetation), compared to only 10% from mature forest areas (Ingalls and Roth, 2018). The promotion of agrobiodiversity thus increases both systemic and discursive resources of the livelihoods-based development project as it aligns with the dominant strategy to use natural resources for poverty alleviation. Furthermore, the figures imply that ‘spared’ forests produce lower NTFP values while industrial tree plantations produce almost none, giving rise to questioning land sparing as the dominant approach towards reforestation and forest regrowth.

⁷ Many stakeholders admit that the recent crop booms, especially in contract farming arrangements, for maize, cassava, job’s tears and the like have increased the degradation of land as farmers abandon agricultural lands after these intensive crops have made it unproductive (interview 9, 17).

Table 1 summarizes the above findings and provides an overview of the power-laden trajectory of the ongoing forest transition in Laos, before we discuss implications of these findings for forests and people in Laos and beyond.

Table 1
Power-laden forest transitions. Visions, strategies, actors and power resources to control and transform the forests in Lao PDR (own elaboration and abstraction, based on interviews and other sources).

	centralized state-control over forests land sparing approach	decentralized control over forests land sharing approach	
	extractivist development project	green development project	livelihoods-based development project
vision of the forest	state-controlled land for extractivist activities and national security	increase forest cover by putting ‘underutilized’ land into more productive use, both through conservation and reforestation	multifunctional landscapes that combine agricultural and forest use
accumulation strategy	commodification of forests (for timber, mining, hydropower, cash crops, etc.) to raise state revenues	commodification of forests for carbon sequestration to raise state revenues	commodification of agrobiodiversity for local livelihoods (upland) rice production for food security
political-spatial strategies	state-led timber extraction large-scale private land concessions through FDI from neighboring countries eradication of shifting cultivation private investors in extractive industries (esp. from China, Thailand, Vietnam) military-controlled forest enterprises state institutions (esp. MEM, MAF, MPI) International Financial Institutions (IFI)	private industrial tree plantations in (degraded) state forest landoffsetting for extractivist activities results-based payments from REDD+ tree plantation companies environmental conservation NGOs UNFCCC Green Climate Fund (World Bank) FAO state institutions (MONRE, NIER, parts of DOF)	participatory land-use planning (pFALUPAM) collection of NTFP
institutional actors			state institutions (DALAM/MAF, parts of DAFO, NAFRI), especially on the district level (inter)national NGOs and researchers selected development co-operation
systemic power resources	high economic growth rates through FDI from neighboring countries	merge economic and environmental interests through industrial tree plantations	revenues from the commodification of NTFP
discursive power resources	supremacy of sedentary agriculture and industrial forestry over shifting cultivation and extensive agroforestry practices	productive use of ‘degraded’ shifting cultivation land	support of food security and local livelihoods (especially in the Lao uplands)
institutional power resources	personal resources of key government institutions	high-level staff from NGOs and donor organizations that controls international financial flows (e. g., from REDD+)	partial recognition of local land use maps

4. Interrogating power and politics in forest transitions

Based on the above analysis of strategies, visions and power resources to mobilize and transform the Laotian forests, this section discusses implications for forests and people as well as for the role of power and politics in forest transitions (research) in Lao PDR and beyond. Looking at forest transitions not only as an increase in tree cover but as a power-laden process sheds light to the “constellation of interests entangled in negotiations over forest change and draws attention to why (and to whom) different aspects of quantitative and qualitative change matter” (Kull, 2017, p. 468).

Dominant government and party institutions have long controlled and transformed the Laotian forests for timber extraction. At the same time, (limited) forest conservation has been interlinked with national security concerns and military control. Overlogging and the uncontrolled expansion of concessions and infrastructure (especially mining, hydropower, agricultural and tree plantations) have led to rapid deforestation and decreasing returns on investments. An alliance of international (donor) organizations, national state institutions and companies therefore frames green development strategies – such as offsetting from extractive industries, results-based payments from REDD+ and especially private industrial tree plantations – as an opportunity to *modernize* the course of extractive development and merge economic goals with progress in reforestation and carbon sequestration. Due to the minor revenues from offsetting schemes and REDD+, however, private industrial tree plantations currently serve as the major strategy to merge economic and environmental concerns. Furthermore, due to the strategic importance of investments from neighboring countries – especially China, Vietnam and Thailand – the further consolidation of these green development strategies will also depend on systemic resources, that is, investments from these countries. The focus on *degraded* state forests as strategic locations for industrial tree plantations and REDD+ also helps to mobilize discursive resources against upland Lao people and their practices (Lestrelin, 2010; see also, Scheidel and Work, 2018). The opening of 600,000 ha of degraded state forest land for tree plantations may therefore put further pressure on multifunctional forest landscapes, including shifting cultivation. The discursive mobilization of degraded land for environmental narratives employs a continuum to put underutilized land into more productive use – both in economic and in carbon-related terms (see also, Baird, 2014).

While rooted in Laos’ historical and geographical context, our analysis provides important insights for forest transition research in general, especially on power and politics as well as on quality and functions of forests. While forest transition research has mainly focused on the quantitative increase in tree and forest cover for many years (e.g., Meyfroidt and Lambin, 2011), our results confirm that “quality matters as much as quantity” (Kull, 2017, p. 469) and that – depending on context and power relations – forests can indeed mean many things, ranging from economic, social and ecological functions (Chazdon et al., 2016): from old growth conservation forests to industrial tree plantations, from state forest estates for timber extraction to multifunctional landscapes that integrate food security with ecosystem services. For decades, governments have mainly focused on the economic function of forests, both through the extraction of timber but also through logged forests that are converted into agricultural or industrial lands. At the same time, the forests have – as in the Lao uplands – had an important security functions for the state (see also, Peluso and Vandergeest, 2011). Whereas these strategies have capitalized on *stabilized or decreasing* forests (through timber extraction or conversion of forests into mining, agricultural or hydropower concessions), green state and international institutions increasingly aim to commodify *increasing* forests, hence, forests’ ecological function for carbon sequestration and biodiversity (see also, Benjaminen and Kaarhus, 2018). These strategies largely neglect the social functions, that is, the immediate livelihood dimension of multifunctional landscapes, including forests, for local people (Dressler et al., 2016). In Lao PDR, especially in the uplands,

multifunctional landscapes integrate diverse practices of upland rice cultivation, NTFP collection as well as selective permanent agriculture and tree planting with rubber or eucalyptus and the like (Ingxay et al., 2019; Vongkhamho et al., 2019). Together, these practices emphasize “multi-purpose uses of agricultural and forest land [that are] consistent with traditional cultural and agroecological systems” (Ingxay et al., 2019). Whereas shifting cultivators and peasants also commodify the forests (e.g., through the commercialization of NTFP), the livelihoods-based strategies emphasize the integrated social and ecological functions of forests that increase the resilience of both livelihoods and ecosystems (Catacutan et al., 2017).

These differences in forests also imply that the benefits from forest transitions are unequally distributed. Throughout the world, the focus on both timber extraction and carbon sequestration through REDD+ has excluded local users and their extensive land use practices from (the benefits from) forests in favor of centralized state institutions and international organizations (Barr and Sayer, 2012; Cole et al., 2017; Phelps et al., 2010). Both historical and contemporary forest transitions, therefore, often co-evolve with dynamic processes of (centralized) state formation that separate forests from people (Pichler et al., 2021a). Related to this, reforestation and forest regrowth in the course of forest transitions tend to focus predominantly on *land sparing* at the expense of *land sharing* and more integrated forms of land use (Mertz and Mertens, 2017; Thaler, 2017). While this simplifies forest functions it also simplifies the users in that it tends to separate and exclude local land users that rely on multifunctional forests. From a livelihoods perspective, research in other countries of the Global South has shown that “more equitable forest governance [may] support land sharing with diverse, extensive livelihoods in various landscapes” (Dressler et al., 2016, p. 75). Hence, an emphasis on politics and governance is indeed key (Riggs et al., 2018) to better understand the mechanisms and institutions that guarantee access to and control of (the benefits from) forests (Pichler et al., 2021b).

5. Conclusion

This article has shown that forest transitions are contested political processes. We approached this insight through developing a conceptual framework rooted in political ecology and critical state theory and applied it to analyze the ongoing forest transition in Lao PDR, identifying three development projects and comparing their political-spatial strategies and power resources. We found that the forest transition in Laos is embedded in a dominant extractivist development project that transforms forests through timber extraction and large-scale land acquisitions while forest conservation is strongly rooted in security concerns. As these strategies increasingly show cracks, green development strategies that focus on offsetting, results-based payments from REDD+ and industrial tree plantations increasingly gain ground in an effort to modernize the extractivist development trajectory but its importance is still fragmented. With regard to systemic power resources, the green development project has yet to seriously challenge the dominant course of development as financial flows from extractivist activities far outweigh green finance. At the moment, the expansion of industrial tree plantations on degraded state forest land is seen as the most powerful strategy to align extractivist and green interests. On the margins, we have identified a livelihoods-based development project that promotes forests as parts of multifunctional landscapes and derives its main power resources from the integration of local livelihood concerns. Yet, the bottom-up and localized strategies, especially participatory land-use planning and the decentralized commercialization of agrobiodiversity, remain something of an ill-fit within the state logics of channeling revenues from forests into state bureaucracies and therefore only reproduce on the margins.

Our research – delving into the particular pathways through which converging and diverging strategies are worked out through forest politics – shows that the underlying logics and intended outcomes of

forest regrowth and reforestation vary, as do their intended distributional outcomes. Dominant strategies in both land use and climate change mitigation policies, including REDD+ and industrial tree plantations, firmly rest in land sparing strategies that often prioritize economic profits over local livelihoods, with important justice implications. While extractivist development strategies are generally seen as zero-sum, diverting revenue streams from local communities to investment companies and state agencies, green development strategies rationalize its investments through a positive-sum framing, emphasizing both local and non-local benefits. Notwithstanding these differences, both roll out across a pre-existing landscape of asymmetric power relations that play a decisive role in shaping their outcomes. The green development project, whatever its explicit intentions, is yet susceptible to elite capture and continually runs the risk of decentering local needs and interests and rendering these subsidiary to non-local aims.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Melanie Pichler: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing, Visualization. **Micah Ingalls:** Writing - review & editing.

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